

“Geological Definition of the Subsurface Pressure System and Its Significance in Hydrocarbon Exploration”

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ABSTRACT Lithology and principal stress are the primary factors influencing the development of the subsurface pore pressure profile. The distribution of lithology creates conditions that lead to compartmentalization in both geological time and space. Identifying the paleoenvironment and understanding sediment distribution within a basin, along with the dynamics of sedimentation and tectonics, are essential for understanding subsurface pressure systems. While most basins are mature regarding shallow prospectivity, they remain immature for deeper plays. The scarcity of deep calibration data makes pressure prediction a challenging task. The importance of pore pressure prediction cannot be overstated, as errors can be costly while drilling.

Understanding the mechanisms of overpressure generation and the regional geology is closely connected to pressure distribution. Each depositional environment has its own pore pressure profile. Therefore, an integrated geological approach is recommended to develop a reliable model for exploration. To understand the geological factors affecting overpressure distribution, analysis of pressure data is necessary to assess the influence of individual lithostratigraphic units and the distribution of low-permeability mudrocks and other seals within those units. The lateral spread of overpressures may be structurally controlled. It can also be partly affected by the interaction of permeable proximal deltaic sediments, low net-to-gross ratios, and disconnected shelf-margin and slope facies. The onset of overpressure is more broadly influenced by regional shale distributions, which are most developed during the maximum flooding stage.

The analysis also involves a complex relationship between distal sealing facies distributions and their proximal permeable correlatives. Broadly, where sandier deltaic/shelfal facies are connected to the surface, they allow rapid pressure dissipation and are consequently hydrostatically pressured. In more distal pro-delta/seaboard facies, lower permeability facies do not enable effective pressure dissipation, and overpressures begin to develop. Higher burial rates and distal facies development coincide; thus, increased overpressure generation typically occurs in facies developed at the shelf margin or beyond. Examples from the North Sea and the Gulf of Mexico are presented to illustrate the importance of the geological definition of subsurface pressure systems in petroleum exploration, particularly in the context of petroleum entrapment.

Key words: Pore pressure prediction, Geology, Pressure cell, Loading, Unloading, Protected trap, Fault valve, Top seal, Blown trap, Sweet spot, Headroom, and Vertical effective stress.

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INTRODUCTION

Oil exploration is essential for meeting the world's energy demands and supporting economic growth. There are two main types: offshore and onshore, each with its own advantages and environmental challenges. Understanding subsurface conditions is crucial, and pore pressure studies help identify risks and potential for extraction. Pore pressure prediction assumes that sands and nearby shales reach equilibrium pressure over time. Sands decrease porosity from about 39% to 49% and 15% to 25% as they compact under pressure at depths of 2 to 3 km¹. Clays, starting with porosities of 65% to 80%, continue to compact at greater depths, reducing their porosities to 5% to 10%¹¹. Shales experience more significant compaction than sands. Tools measure formation pressure by inserting a probe, mainly in sands. Therefore, pore pressure in shales is compared with that in adjacent sands. While most basins show maturity in shallow prospecting, they still lack maturity for deeper plays. The scarcity of deep calibration data makes pressure prediction a challenging task. Accurate prediction of pore pressure is critically important.

Why pressure prediction is important

Pressure prediction is important during exploration for several reasons. Accurately forecasting pore pressure is crucial for designing wells effectively. Overestimating can lead to unnecessary costs and damage, while underestimating can cause abandonment or safety issues. It should also be included in risk assessments. Understanding how pressure affects processes such as hydrocarbon migration is essential for prospect generation and is key to avoiding drilling hazards and optimizing well design (Figure 1). It illustrates the impact of pore pressure on prospect risking, safety, well design, and volumetrics, from left to right, in a clockwise direction.

Figure 1: Importance of pore pressure

Knowing the pre-drill formation pore pressure is essential for safe and efficient well drilling. It helps in choosing mud weights, casing points, and completions. Understanding pore pressure also aids in recognizing abnormal pressures and their causes related to geological factors. A summary of the significance of pore pressure in the petroleum exploration and production is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Utility of pore pressure in petroleum exploration and production

Overpressure generation and retention

Overpressures can be created by various mechanisms that either increase the volume of fluids in the subsurface or decrease the available pore space. Overpressure generation mechanisms include disequilibrium compaction, hydrocarbon generation, aquathermal expansion, and diagenesis^{III}.

The contribution of each overpressure mechanism heavily depends on the geological environment. Disequilibrium compaction (or under-compaction) is a significant cause of overpressure in Tertiary deltas. During burial, fresh sedimentation increases the load on deeper sediments, leading to compaction and dehydration. In fluvio-deltaic settings, sedimentation rates are very high, and low-permeability shales are common. Here, a high sedimentation rate, combined with the low permeability of the distal argillaceous facies, prevents sediments from de-watering and compacting quickly enough to keep pace with the added overburden load. As a result, the weight of the new overburden is supported by pore fluids rather than the grain structure of the under-compacted rock. This causes increased pore pressure in shales and permeable units surrounded by low-permeability shales.

Regardless of the cause of overpressure, the observed magnitude and distribution of overpressures are heavily influenced by the distribution of high- and low-permeability intervals in the subsurface. For example, sands have high permeability and act as fluid flow pathways; a connected sand system will always maintain a constant overpressure in the water phase. Shales and marls, with low permeability, can serve as barriers to fluid flow, supporting pressure gradients. When a permeable system is connected to the surface, its pressure will be hydrostatic. Although shales and other tight lithologies, such as distal carbonates and marls, have extremely low permeability, fluid flow through them still occurs over geological timescales. Therefore, overpressures are a dynamic phenomenon, controlled by both the rates of pressure generation and dissipation via fluid flow within the subsurface. Ultimately, given enough geological time, overpressures will dissipate due

to fluid flow. Pressure readings from wells are thus a snapshot in geological time of a system that is gradually decompressing.

Why is the Pressure Generating Mechanism Important?

The mechanism impacts the timing of geopressuring & the stress history. Differing mechanisms impact rock properties in different ways (e.g. porosity/permeability evolution during compaction behaviour, acoustic properties). Some mechanisms are more likely to cause pressure disequilibrium between mudrocks and sands. Some mechanisms can be modeled using velocities and/or basin modeling, while others cannot be easily modeled. Compaction disequilibrium is the most critical mechanism in basins of interest in oil exploration, but this is rapidly changing as we drill deeper and in more complex settings. The plot of shale interval velocity versus the vertical effective stress in an undercompaction-driven overpressures and unloading-driven mechanisms illustrates the importance of understanding the pressure-generating mechanism, as the pressures generated differ markedly in magnitude (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Shale interval velocity vs. Vertical effective stress under different pressure mechanisms.

How the pressure generation mechanism is understood

Understanding the pressure mechanisms and their impact on the relationship between porosity and effective stress is crucial for predicting pore pressure, particularly in complex geological settings and high-temperature environments. Overpressures most often result from undercompaction or unloading processes. Overpressure caused by undercompaction typically exhibits a direct relationship between effective stress and porosity, whereas overpressure related to unloading does not follow a clear trend in porosity. The specific unloading mechanism can be identified by observing changes and distortions in effective stress and velocity patterns during the unloading process.

Overpressured formations display several properties compared to a normally pressured section at the same depth^{IV}: (1) higher porosities, (2) lower bulk densities, (3) lower effective stresses, (4) higher temperatures, (5) lower interval velocities, and (6) higher Poisson's ratios.

Changes in pore pressure can be identified through formation evaluation tools, including sonic, resistivity, porosity, and density logs. These logs illustrate how pore pressure affects rock properties through the relationships between compaction, porosity, density, and acoustic properties. As rocks undergo compaction, their porosity decreases while density increases, affecting other properties. When rock stiffness or pore pressure opposes compaction, the process slows down. Undercompacted rocks continue to follow typical compaction trends but exhibit higher porosity and lower velocities compared to normally compacted rocks at the same depth^V. These differences are observable in log displays (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Velocity and density logs illustrate the physical characteristics of normally compacting rocks (represented by blue trend lines), undercompacted rocks (indicated by orange trend lines), and unloading (depicted by red trend lines)^V.

It has been found that overpressure-generating mechanisms have direct control over the shape of the pore pressure profile. Although there are various reasons for overpressure generation, broadly, they can be categorized into loading or disequilibrium compaction and unloading (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Shale interval velocity vs. Vertical effective stress and Pore pressure plots under loading and unloading mechanisms

Thus, it is possible to distinguish the pressure-generating mechanism in a particular stratigraphy at a locale in a basin.

Influence of Geology and Overpressure Generating Mechanism

To understand the breaching potential of a petroleum trap, the shape of the pore pressure profile is key. The root cause analysis of the pore pressure profile's shape is related to the depositional environment of the sediments and the mechanism generating overpressure. The pore pressure profile and the type of pressure ramp depend on the geological history of the area, which may include tectonic effects or variations in lithofacies distribution.

Geological Perceptions

Walther's law connects the vertical arrangement of rock environments to their lateral spread. Facies maps were created from studies in central and coastal swamps to analyze permeable and sealing facies by stratigraphic unit. These maps aid in understanding permeability architecture and overpressures, particularly in relation to shelf-margin facies. The facies distribution in a coastal to deep water bathymetry is illustrated in Figure 6^{VI}. Understanding the geology and formation history of a basin is crucial for predicting pore pressure, and it is often not fully understood (Figure 7).

Figure 6: A conceptual diagram illustrates the possible facies distribution along a cross-section extending from the inner shelf to the bathyal environments^{VI}

Uplift and erosion: In a post-depositional marine setting, sediments that are uplifted due to tectonic plate movement become exposed above mean sea level. This causes erosion of the exposed surface. After a hiatus, deposition begins again on this eroded surface. The sediments deposited after this event may or may not have a similar imprint from any further tectonic activity. In many cases, it is found that the imprints of tectonic activity in both these geological episodes differ and can be differentiated in the field or by geophysical data through an angular unconformity. The upliftment and erosion cause the deeper pressures to be transferred vertically

with a lesser amount of overburden^{VII}(Figure 8). The pressure ramp in this situation is usually steep. This process is also known as unloading.

Figure 7: Deep marine shales is what we are referring to as “prodelta shales”

Figure 8: Stages in the development of unloading and the resultant pore pressure profile^{VII}.

Influence of Geology on Pore Pressure Profiles

Subsurface geopressure profiles largely depend on lithology and principal stresses. Vertical stress arises from the combined weight of sediments and water. Offshore water depth directly impacts the extent of the regional hydrostatic-lithostatic pressure envelope. Understanding the seismic reflector architecture is essential for identifying depositional cycles in clastic basins and, consequently, for building pore pressure profiles^{VI}. Regardless of the origin of overpressure, its magnitude and distribution are heavily influenced by the dispersal of high- and low-permeability layers in the subsurface.

For example, sands have high permeability and serve as pathways for fluid flow. Typically, formations like shales or claystone that are impermeable and undergo rapid burial maintain a pore pressure (PP) trend that is parallel or nearly parallel to the lithostatic or overburden pressure (OBP) profile, keeping the vertical effective stress (VES) constant ($VES = OBP - PP$) if they are in pressure equilibrium^{VIII}. However, the shallowest overburden formation, even if less permeable,

usually stays hydrostatic to some depth below the surface before pressure gradually rises to a steady VES condition^{VI}. Conversely, permeable reservoirs with good lateral connectivity are generally hydrostatically pressured, enabling fluid to reach equilibrium with surface conditions through the sandstones^{IX & III}. In deeper sandstones, pressure deviations from this trend may occur due to pressure compartmentalization by shale seals. Still, the PP profile generally stays parallel to hydrostatic pressure (HP) trends and maintains a constant overpressure (OP = PP - HP), unless lighter hydrocarbons in extended columns cause inflation. As a result, subsurface pore pressure profiles typically follow either a constant VES or a constant OP pattern (Figure 9). Geological insights were utilized as a reference alongside the calibration data to determine whether a constant OP model or a constant VES model should represent a specific formation^{VIII}.

Figure 9– Schematic pore pressure profiles based on constant OP and constant VES for various sand-shale sequences; the thick blue arrow for the case of pressure regression indicates that the sand is plumbed to hydrostatic pressure at shallower depths^{VIII}

Seals occur in nearly all types of lithology, but they are most commonly identified in lithologies such as shale, evaporites, and salt. All seals experience leakage over time, and the edges of most seals are diffuse. The most effective method for identifying seals is through the analysis of pressure data obtained from well tests, which can be represented in simple pressure-depth plots or through anomalous production that indicates barriers between wells. Fault seals present the most significant challenges, as their characteristics can change rapidly both along the strike and vertically within the fault system, influenced by lithology juxtapositions, shale gouge, and/or the direction of stress^X.

In reality, the litho-facies distribution can vary with changes in paleo-depositional environments within the same basin. It may thus show variations in pore pressure profiles at different locations within that basin. Figure 10 illustrates a scenario with the possible facies distribution and the corresponding pore pressure profiles along a cross-section from the shelf area to the bathyal zone. Eustatic changes causing progradation and retrogradation of shelf sediments will lead to variations in facies distribution. Shelf areas dominated by coarse, permeable clastics display hydrostatic or near-hydrostatic pore pressure profiles up to a deeper level, beneath which thin layers of pressure seals (mudrock and shale) may cause a steep pressure rise. As water depth increases, the dominance of the impermeable layer grows, resulting in more gradual overpressurization, and pore pressure profiles become more or less parallel to overburden pressures (Figure 10). These

variations in pore pressure profiles with changing paleo-depositional settings are crucial for understanding the importance of normalizing offset pressure data^{XI}. For example, if pressure data from shelf areas needs to be used for modeling and comparing pore pressure predictions in bathyal-region prospects, simply transferring the data will not give an accurate picture. Those pressure points must be normalized when extrapolating them in depth.

Figure 10: Conceptual diagram to illustrate variation in subsurface pore pressure profiles with changing lithofacies along a cross-section extending from shelf to bathyal environments; MFS = maximum flooding surface^{XI}

Marine Depositional Setup: In a typical marine depositional setting, eustatic changes leading to the progradation and retrogradation of shelf sediments result in variations in facies distribution. Areas with mostly coarse and permeable clastics on the shelf tend to have hydrostatic or near-hydrostatic pore pressure profiles up to a certain depth, beyond which thin layers of pressure seals (shales) can cause a steep increase in pressure. As water depth increases, impermeable layers become more dominant, leading to a gradual increase in overpressurization and pore pressure profiles that align with overburden pressures (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Deep water Pore Pressure profile

Data required for defining the pressure system

Pressure information about the subsurface can be obtained from direct pressure measurements taken from permeable units, such as Repeat Formation Test (RFT), Formation Interval Test (FIT/FTT), Reservoir Characterization Instrument (RCI), Modular Formation Dynamic Tester (MDT), Drill Stem Test (DST), and kicks. Alternatively, it can be derived from indirect data, such as mud weight measurements and pressure calculations based on log responses or seismic velocities. Ideally, these data should be available for every well and should represent the full overpressure profile of the system or cell. In this study, we mainly rely on mud weights, kicks, FIT/FTTs, and RFTs. In such cases, the daily drilling reports are crucial for assessing the reliability of mud weight data, determining whether the well is under- or overbalanced at any time, and understanding if changes in mud weight are responses to hole conditions or pre-planned adjustments. Signs of underbalanced drilling include decreases in mud weight due to gas cutting, increases in drilling rate (ROP) resulting in drilling breaks, borehole stability issues, and sloughing of shales or shale cavings.

Rationale of the Stratigraphic Framework

To comprehend and forecast pressure distribution within a basin, pressure data and the surrounding sediments where pressure regimes are confined should be analyzed within a comprehensive and consistent stratigraphic framework. This analysis should be based on well ties and regional mapping, including GDE (gross depositional environment) maps, fault polygons, and horizons.

Well-calibrated stratigraphic scheme. The pressures must be accurately placed within the correct stratigraphic context. In this case, chronostratigraphic or sequence stratigraphic information is more valuable than lithostratigraphic picks. Extensive seismic coverage and detailed fault mapping—particularly where faulting is known to confine pressures (potential pressure cell barriers)—are essential. Other valuable data, such as lithology and depositional facies interpretations, can become important because they are key elements in understanding the stratigraphic or permeability architecture of the basin. Leak-off test data, and to a lesser extent, formation integrity/limit test data, are also helpful to define the fracture gradient.

Mud weight alone cannot and should not be used as a proxy for pressure without careful qc of the drilling data to determine whether the well was drilled in balance. Examples of wells where MFS appears to control overpressure distribution are illustrated, alongside examples where the MFS is not the control.

Finely Balanced Drilling example: A fine example of this is well I-1 in the Niger Delta, from which four pressure transitions are identifiable in the mud profile (Figure 12). In each case, gas-cut mud, drilling breaks, and flows were observed, and mud weights were increased accordingly. A limited number of FTT/FIT readings demonstrate that pressures calculated directly from the mud densities are within a few hundred psi of the actual formation pressures. Here, mud weight is a good proxy for formation pressure.

Figure 12: Typical pressure data (mud weight and RFTs) with key stratigraphy and commentary on the left and the right (Well I-1), Niger Delta indicating finely balanced drilling

When geological-based methods can be employed

Traditionally, the geological definition of the pressure system has been confined to pressure cell analysis, which requires accurate well control. Pressure prediction from seismic velocity analysis and basin modelling has generally been used in less well-calibrated settings. These methods rely on several assumptions that are especially suitable for shale-dominated systems. A geological method has the advantage of not relying on assumptions about the causal mechanism behind overpressure. Here, it is essential to use the geological workflow for detailing pressure distributions within a broad geological framework (Figure 13). With limited calibration data, defining the pressure system geologically offers a framework for understanding the likely pressure distribution. As more data becomes available within this framework, it serves as a predictive tool for subsequent prospects, allowing the estimation of column lengths and pore pressures at the bit. The geological definition of the pressure system also provides the input model for pressure modeling using basin models. It offers a framework for selecting appropriate calibration wells for seismic PPP understanding when seismic pressure prediction is valid (mainly in shale sections). Given the unconstrained pressures in the deep section of the basin in question, an integrated approach should be taken, combining pore pressure predictions with a geological approach that constrains historical information.

Figure 13: Workflow in pore pressure studies at various stages of exploration

Pressure distribution and pressure cells

Studies using geology to constrain the overpressure system mainly focus on the geological aspects of pressure prediction, especially the concept of pressure cells. Pressure cells are volumes of sediments with roughly the same overpressure (pressure above the hydrostatic depth trend) and generally share the same pressure attribute. This occurs over intervals with sufficient permeability to behave as a connected brine column on a geologic timescale. A constant overpressure cell may be bounded by vertical seal (Figure 14A) and/or lateral seals (Figure 14B). Typically, these cells are mapped using well control to constrain them. Once a pressure cell is mapped in three dimensions, it can be used to predict pore pressure for any proposed well that intersects it. They tend to be bound by structural features (e.g., faults) or layers of low-permeability sediments (such as shale or salt domes). Consequently, pressure cells can be distributed either horizontally or vertically. In the horizontal case, boundaries are often structural features or rapid facies changes, while in the vertical case, pressure cells are separated by tight facies distributions.

While pressure cells are a useful concept, they represent only part of the geological definition of the pressure system. The geologically based pressure prediction requires a more detailed integration of the geological model (e.g., gross depositional environment – GDE) or gross stratigraphic architecture with the known pressure distribution (Figures 9 & 10). Regardless of the cause of overpressure, its distribution and often its magnitude are controlled by the distribution of permeable and impermeable facies that make up the basin's fill (or permeability architecture). Once the depositional environment and facies distribution are interpreted, and pressure distributions are well-constrained, it then becomes possible to predict pressures throughout a basin qualitatively.

If the pressure cell is defined by several well penetrations and good seismic mapping (Figure 14A), then this is the most effective method for predicting pore pressure. Constant overpressure cells develop through lateral flow (Basin Model – Lateral Flow) and may also be constrained by a leak point at a blown trap, in which case, they can help identify protected traps. A pressure cell could also be a volume of rock with a constant vertical effective stress (pressure below the overburden). This occurs over intervals of low permeability and sealing and is a natural result of disequilibrium compaction. If a sealing unit is thick and extensive with a low net-to-gross ratio, such a pressure cell can extend over very large intervals, as seen in the Cretaceous in the Eastern Gulf of Mexico and the North Atlantic (Figure 15). Mapping the extent and thickness of the sealing rock can also be used as a method for predicting pore pressure, known as the equivalent seal method.

Figure 14A. Example from the Gulf of Mexico indicating lateral and vertical communication, and 14B from the North Sea indicating lateral pressure cell boundaries.

Figure 15: Cretaceous pressure data and Cretaceous interval in yellow showing a constant VES pressure cell

Connected or Disconnected

The vertical and lateral pressure seals are illustrated in Figure 16. In the case of vertical communication, the pressure at the crest will be significantly higher than when the well is vertically sealed due to the hydrocarbon column effect. The pressure data and analysis would be invaluable in determining if intermediate seals are present. An overprint of geology on connectivity and pressure distribution is discernible from the pressure data analysis.

Figure 16: Significance of connected and disconnected for intermediate seals

Analogue: Pressure distribution (cells) within the UK North Sea Central Graben

The Mesozoic sediments of the Central North Sea are mostly part of the syn-rift. In the North Sea, these deep targets are separated laterally by shales, high salt walls, and diapirs. These features, along with extensional faulting, create lateral flow barriers with extremely low permeability. These barriers divide regions with varying levels of overpressure related to their depth, temperature, and burial histories. The deep overpressured rocks of the Central North Sea are thus divided into “cells”

of similar overpressure, bounded by faults and salt (Figure 17). A detailed understanding of the geological model enhances comprehension of the likely pressure system away from well control.

Figure 17: Pressure distribution (cells) within the UK North Sea Central Graben

Using the pressure cell concept to predict blown and protected traps

An assessment of the risk of a blown trap is essential for any prospect in an overpressured regime. Identifying the expected prospect of overpressure is vital, and pressure cell mapping will ultimately enable this. The magnitude of the overpressure will determine whether the crest of the prospect is too shallow to retain a hydrocarbon column, and whether the increase in hydrostatic head pressure generated by the buoyancy of hydrocarbons relative to water could have fractured the top seal. Therefore, in any given pressure cell, the viability of the prospects within will depend on the depth of each crest and the overpressure.

Figure 18: Protected trap concept

In such a case where the shallowest target of a pressure cell is hydraulically blown, the deeper targets will be subsequently protected (Figure 18). The pressure will be regulated in a trap that is hydraulically connected to a leak point. The pressure in the reservoir cannot increase beyond its current pressure. Trap B is referred to as a protected trap; it is safe from top seal failure. In blowing

the crest of a pressure cell, the overpressure is prevented from building any further (as this effectively allows pressure to be released from the cell), and the result is that the deeper prospects are protected from further pressure build-up, enabling them to retain hydrocarbon columns. The depth of the prospect crest and length of any hydrocarbon column relative to the spill point will, however, determine if the prospect is likely to be under-filled or not.

Assessing the risk of a blown trap is crucial for any prospect in an overpressured area. Knowing the expected overpressure is essential, as pressure cell mapping helps identify this. The level of overpressure influences whether a prospect can sustain a hydrocarbon column and if the top seal might crack due to increased pressure from buoyant hydrocarbons. In a pressure cell, prospects depend on crest depth and overpressure. If a shallow target blows, deeper targets are safer and can retain hydrocarbon columns, preventing further pressure buildup. An example is the Shearwater pressure cell in the UK North Sea, where Martha is blown, but Juno and Shearwater remain protected, although under-filled (Figures 19 & 20)^{XII&XIII}.

Figure 19: Schematic diagram adapted from Winefield et al. (2005)^{XII}. The idea is founded on hydraulic fracturing (i.e., pore pressures are crucial, rather than aquifer pressures). The Shearwater trap represents the deepest formation and is safeguarded by the Martha and possibly the Juno structures.

Figure 20: Schematic representation of a dynamic trapping mechanism in overpressured reservoirs (modified and adapted from Sales (1997) in Winefield 2005)^{XIII}

The pressure in the aquifer within the pressure cell is governed by the crest of the shallowest structure (A). Any hydrocarbons entering the trap lack enough 'headroom' to be retained and are lost through vertical leakage at the top seal. This structure is similar to the Martha structure in the Shearwater pressure cell. The downdip structure (B) can hold a hydrocarbon column because the updip valve protects it. However, the maximum height of this column is still limited by the headroom between the aquifer gradient and the top seal line, which is effectively underfilled. This situation resembles the Shearwater field. The deepest structure (C) is sufficiently deep to reach the structural spill point, so the maximum hydrocarbon column is limited by the structural closure rather than the top seal's strength (Figure 21).

Figure 21: A schematic representation of a dynamic trap system, modified by Winefield et al. (2005) based on the work of Sales (1997)^{XIII} and Converse et al. (2000)^{XIV}. All components (A-C) exhibit hydraulic connectivity. This is illustrated in the Pressure vs Depth plot, where all fields demonstrate a shared aquifer gradient.

In the Genesis and Popeye hydrocarbon traps of the Gulf of Mexico, the reservoir pore pressures in the deeper fields can't reach their specific fracture pressures because of a pressure valve at the crests of the shallower sands. This setup allows a hydrocarbon column to be maintained within these traps, protecting it from breaching. Even if pore pressures increase, possibly due to additional burial, the pressure valve in the shallower sands can still maintain the integrity of the columns, as it provides a reliable seal within the hydrocarbon reservoirs (see Figure 22).

Figure 22: A simplified diagram of the Popeye/Genesis minibasin is presented. Figure B depicts a Pressure-Depth plot that emphasises the structural leak point alongside a safeguarded deeper hydrocarbon-bearing trap. The symbols σ_h' TRAP and σ_h' denote the effective stress^{XV}

Fault-valve behaviour of petroleum traps

An increased reservoir pressure at a critical fault segment can trigger fluid flow along and out of the trap. This cyclical process, known as the fault-valve mechanism, originates from Sibson's 1990 model^{XVI}(Figure 23). Although it is well known that fluid movement along faults can impact the hydrocarbon column in a trap, using the concept of critically stressed faults to evaluate fault-bound traps is uncommon. The critically stressed fault and its fault-valve model are now regarded as credible trapping mechanisms, affecting exploration, appraisal, and production activities. This is particularly important because faults with specific orientations may leak at fluid pressures below the minimum horizontal stress.

Figure 23: Assessment procedure of the risk of a blown trap

Top Seal Failure Analysis in Prospect Generation

Failure of the top seal can occur when fluids in the pore spaces overcome either the capillary entry pressure or the mechanical failure strength of the seal. Mechanical seal failure occurs when pore pressure exceeds the fracture pressure (minimum principal stress plus tensile strength). At high

vertical effective stress (VES), even with the effect of the hydrocarbon column on the brine pressure profile—which is also the shale pore pressure—breaching of the top seal usually does not occur. However, with a narrower window between pore pressure and fracture pressure, it often cannot support a large hydrocarbon column or a breached trap, as seen in many cases. The situation worsens in deepwater shallow reservoirs, where VES is narrow by default. Figure 24 to the left shows a conceptual illustration of a hypothetical case of penetration at the top of the crest in a deepwater setting. A wider VES and a larger window between pore pressure (PP) and fracture pressure (FP) allow the hydrocarbon column to remain intact. Conversely, breaching of the trap, due to a narrower VES and PP-FP window in a similar hypothetical setup, is shown in Figure 24 to the right.

Figure 24. Pressure profile along a well trajectory drilled through the crest. Hypothetical situation for a safe top seal and a breached top seal^{VII}

Hydrocarbons can be stored in areas with high overpressure, provided there is a “protected trap” with a caprock or top seal that is strong enough to withstand mechanical stress. In deepwater environments, shallower reservoirs might have some protection if the seal behaves like a flexible material. A single geological structure can have reservoirs stacked on top of each other, with alternating seals. These are also known as alternating reservoir-seal pairs (RSPs). In many cases, the shallower reservoirs may be damaged at the top. Still, deeper reservoirs in the same structure can be protected if they are not connected to the shallowest damaged reservoir (Figure 25).

Figure 25. Breached and protected traps in stacked reservoirs

Compaction depends on virgin VES (or maximum VES) and thus affects the prediction of reservoir porosity. Unlike seal failure, lower VES benefits reservoir porosity. A “sweet spot” for VES exists where it is low enough to maintain good reservoir porosity but not so low that the seal might break,

leading to leakage. A VES that is too high is also problematic because it reduces reservoir quality by decreasing porosity (Figure 26).

Effective stress is not only essential to understand from a drilling standpoint, but it also exerts a firm control on porosity development. In situations where effective stress is minimal, drilling conditions become challenging, and there may be limited or no space for a hydrocarbon column before buoyancy pressure surpasses the fracture pressure^X.

Figure 26. Schematic diagram showing the interplay between VES and reservoir porosity^{VII}

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Pore pressures are controlled by the geological setting in which the stratigraphy occurs. Pore pressure profiles vary according to the gross depositional environment. The main control on overpressure distribution is the relationship between permeable and impermeable facies. The occurrence of low-permeability seals must be established in the context of petroleum exploration, considering both prospectivity and safety aspects. Understanding the occurrences of reservoir facies, the associated pressure regimes, and placing them in the correct stratigraphic context within exploration models helps define top seal integrity and prospectivity, making the model more robust. Notions of Geological processes and thoughts are the key drivers in estimating pore pressure preservation and dissipation. A good handle on the pressure magnitude is essential for trouble-free operations and derisking the well design. The related workflow, along with examples from key basins, illustrates the importance of understanding the geological context of pore pressures. It is anticipated that this workflow will serve as a springboard for more detailed pore pressure research in the future and aid in deeper play exploration.

REFERENCE

- I. Lundegard, P. D. (1962). Sandstone porosity loss: A “big picture” view of the importance of compaction. *Journal of Sedimentary Petrology*, 32, 250–260.
- II. Sclater, J. G., & Christie, P. A. F. (1980). Continental stretching: An explanation of the post mid-Cretaceous subsidence of the Central North Sea Basin. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 85, 3711–3739.
- III. Osborne, M. J., & Swarbrick, R. E. (1997). Mechanisms for generating overpressure in sedimentary basins: A re-evaluation. *AAPG Bulletin*, 81(6), 1023–1041.

- IV. Dutta, N. (2002). Geopressure prediction using seismic data: Current status and the road ahead. *Geophysics*, 67(6), 2012–2041.
- V. Chopra, S., et al. (2006). Velocity determination for pore-pressure prediction. *CSEG Recorder*, April 2006.
- VI. Shaker, S. S. (2002). Sequence stratigraphy: Key to geopressure profile assessment. *CSEG Recorder*, 27(7), 1–2.
- VII. Purkayastha, A. D. (2020). *Impact of reservoir formation pressure and cap rock integrity in preliminary headroom potential analysis* (Personal communication).
- VIII. Hansen, K. S., et al. (2014). Predrill pore pressure and fracture gradient prediction based on pressure cell models for onshore unconventional gas, Sichuan Basin. *International Petroleum Technology Conference*, Kuala Lumpur, IPTC-18106-MS, 2–3.
- IX. Cayley, G. T. (1987). Hydrocarbon migration in Central North Sea. In J. Brooks & K. W. Glennie (Eds.), *Petroleum geology of north-west Europe* (pp. 549–555). London: Graham and Trotman.
- X. Dolson, J. (2016). Understanding seals, pressures, and hydrodynamics. In *Understanding oil and gas shows and seals in the search for hydrocarbons* (Chap. 4). Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-29710-1_4
- XI. Purkayastha, A. D., & Nair, P. V. (2017). Prospect level normalization of offset pore pressure measurements: Analysis of approaches and their association with regional geology. *Society of Petroleum Engineers (SPE)*, SPE-185394-MS.
- XII. Winefield, P., Gilham, R., & Elsinger, R. L. (2005). Plumbing the depths of the Central Graben: Towards an integrated pressure, fluid and charge model for the Central North Sea HPHT play. In *Petroleum Geology: North-West Europe and Global Perspectives – Proceedings of the 6th Petroleum Geology Conference* (pp. 1301–1316).
- XIII. Sales, J. (1997). [Cited in Winefield, P., Gilham, R., & Elsinger, R. L., 2005]. *Plumbing the depths of the Central Graben*. In *Petroleum Geology: North-West Europe and Global Perspectives – Proceedings of the 6th Petroleum Geology Conference* (pp. 1301–1316).
- XIV. Converse, D. R., et al. (2000). Controls on overpressure in rapidly subsiding basins and implications for failure of top seal. In *Petroleum Systems of South Atlantic Margins*, AAPG Memoir 73, 133–150.
- XV. Seldon, B., & Flemings, P. B. (2005). Reservoir pressure and seafloor venting: Predicting trap integrity in a Gulf of Mexico deepwater turbidite minibasin. *AAPG Bulletin*, 89(2), 193–209.
- XVI. Sibson, R. H. (1990). Conditions for fault-valve behavior. *Geological Society, London, Special Publications*, 54(1), 15–28. <https://doi.org/10.1144/GSL.SP.1990.054.01.02>